

Monitoring the removal of 1- μm Microplastics and Bacteria from secondary-treated wastewater in Spent Coffee Ground Biochar columns with Flow Cytometry

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of pyrolysis temperature on spent-coffee-grounds biochar's surface and chemical characteristics and its impact on the removal of small microplastics (1 μm), a size range challenging to both capture and measure with conventional systems. High-throughput flow cytometry was used to rapidly and accurately quantify traceable 1- μm microplastic spikes, alongside enumerating stained bacterial cells naturally present in secondary-treated wastewater. Filtration column tests at a flow rate of 1 mL/min were performed, with effluent samples collected every 2 min for a real-time analysis of microplastics and bacteria removal. Biochar produced at 500°C exhibited the highest removal capacity, with almost no microplastics detected after filtration tests and over 50% of bacteria retained. In contrast, 300°C biochar showed the lowest removal efficiency for both microplastics and bacteria, while 700°C biochar demonstrated intermediate performances.

Keywords

Biochar-based filtration; emerging contaminants; flow cytometry; microplastics removal; wastewater treatment.

INTRODUCTION

The continuous discharge of microplastics (MP) [1 μm – 5 mm] from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) has been identified as a significant source of plastic pollution in aquatic environments (Monira et al., 2023), highlighting the urgent need for effective and sustainable removal technologies. While WWTPs demonstrate over 90% efficiency in MP removal, this effectiveness is strongly dependent on particle size, with MPs in the micrometer range proven particularly difficult to remove with conventional filtration systems (Talvitie et al., 2017). Most studies, however, focus on particles larger than 20 μm (Dronjak et al., 2023), as monitoring smaller MPs is challenging and not reproducible due to their fluctuating concentrations in influent and effluent wastewater, which increases analysis time, and restricts accurate quantification to a limited number of samples within a feasible timeframe, causing high uncertainty in removal efficiency assessments. Moreover, the complex composition of wastewater, with its high solids content, can mask smaller MPs, often requiring strong chemical pretreatments for separation, which can damage MPs and further complicate the analysis.

Flow cytometry (FCM) is a high-resolution, single-particle analysis technique that detects fluorescence and scattering signals emitted by individual fluorescent particles in the nanometer to micrometer range, enabling their distinction from the background in complex matrices. This study employs FCM to rapidly and accurately identify and quantify traceable 1- μm MPs spiked in secondary-treated wastewater, alongside stained bacteria cells naturally present. Through filtration column tests, the removal performance of spent coffee grounds biochar (SCG-B) for wastewater remediation was evaluated, and the influence of pyrolysis temperature on the adsorptive properties of the manufactured materials was investigated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SCG Biochar – Spent coffee grounds underwent pyrolysis in a N₂-purged (0.1 L/min) horizontal furnace at 300, 500 and 700°C, with a 1-h holding time. The influence of pyrolysis temperature on biochar's chemical and morphological properties (through FTIR, SEM, and granulometry analyses) and its impact on removal efficiency were investigated.

Filtration columns – Three identical glass columns (16 mm diameter, Figure 1) were packed with a 150 mm SCG-biochar layer (grain size: $190 \pm 30 \mu\text{m}$ (D₁₀) – $800 \pm 250 \mu\text{m}$ (D₉₀), Figure 3A), positioned between two 100 mm sand layers (2–4 mm) to prevent biochar loss. Sequential pore volumes (PVs, 10 mL) of the influent solutions were injected from the bottom via a peristaltic pump.

Figure 1. SCG-biochar filtration column.

1- μm MPs – Polystyrene 1- μm spherical particles *Fluoro Max G0100* (ThermoFisher, USA; $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 468 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 508 \text{ nm}$) were used as traceable MPs as they emit green fluorescence that can be easily detected by FCM. MPs were suspended into secondary-treated wastewater to achieve an initial concentration of $0.80 \pm 0.05 \text{ mg/L}$, corresponding to $1430 \pm 90 \text{ MP}/\mu\text{L}$.

Bacterial cells – For the enumeration of bacterial cells via FCM analysis in the effluents before and after filtration, samples were stained with the fluorochrome *SYBR Green I* (Invitrogen, USA, diluted 1:30 in DMSO; $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 495 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 525 \text{ nm}$). 10 μL of dye were added to 1 mL of secondary-treated wastewater samples containing approximately 10^8 – 10^9 cell/L . Samples were incubated in the dark at room temperature for 15 minutes and subsequently analyzed using FCM.

Flow cytometry – For FCM analyses, *Attune NxT* (ThermoFisher, USA) was used, and signals of scattering and fluorescence emitted by 1- μm MPs and bacteria cells were collected and differentiated (Figure 2). Over 100,000 events were counted for each sample to ensure statistically significant data.

Figure 2. Cytograms of 1- μm MP spikes and bacterial cells in secondary-treated wastewater: (i) FSC vs. SSC indicates particle size and surface roughness, and (ii)(iii) BL1 vs. SSC and vs. FSC to differentiate fluorescence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterisation of SCG biochar

SCG demonstrated high potential for biochar production, with higher pyrolysis temperatures reducing yield due to volatile matter loss (mass yields on a dry basis: $57.1 \pm 2.2\%$, $27.7 \pm 1.7\%$, and $26.9 \pm 0.2\%$ at 300, 500, and 700°C, respectively), while biochar pH becomes increasingly alkaline due to the enrichment of ash content (from 4.9 ± 0.7 at 300°C to 7.6 ± 0.2 at 500°C and 8.5 ± 0.3 at 700°C). Raw SCG and biochar produced at 300°C share some key characteristics. Microscopically, their surfaces appear coarse and homogeneous, with a uniform structure (Figure 3C, D). Spectroscopically, both exhibit strong FTIR peaks in the 3000 – 2800 cm^{-1} range, indicative of C-H_n functional groups, which are absent at higher pyrolysis temperatures. As lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose degrade during pyrolysis, functional groups decrease, while the rapid release of volatiles creates active sites that form the porous structure. Higher pyrolysis temperatures enhance porosity, producing the sponge-like morphology observed in 500 and 700°C SCG-biochars (Figure 3E, F).

Figure 3. (A) Granulometric distribution, (B) FTIR spectra, and SEM images of (C) raw SCG and SCG-biochar produced at (D) 300°C, (E) 500°C, and (F) 700°C.

Filtration column tests with SCG biochar

MPs and bacteria removal in filtration columns consisted of 5 phases presented in Figure 4: (i) Pre-equilibration with 10 PVs of distilled water (10 mL/min) to saturate the column; (ii) 3 PVs of secondary-treated wastewater; (iii) 4 PVs of the same wastewater spiked with 1- μm MPs (0.8 mg/L); (iv) 6 PVs to elute suspended MPs. Phases (ii)–(iv) ran at 1 mL/min to ensure a 10-min contact time, with effluent sampling every 2 min for FCM breakthrough curve analysis. (v) Backwashing was performed 3 times with 3 PVs of distilled water (10 mL/min), alternating with air (5 L/min) to suspend and assess particles leaching. The release rate was calculated as the outlet-to-inlet concentration (C_t/C_0) ratio (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Breakthrough curves of (A) bacterial cells and (B) 1- μm MPs in three SCG-biochar filtration columns.

Filtration column test results for bacterial cell removal (Figure 4A) show that the first three PVs represent a transitional phase where the columns are adjusting to the wastewater influent flow, reaching equilibrium after 6 PVs. For bacteria entrapment, the 300°C biochar column was the least effective, retaining only $38 \pm 18\%$ of filtered cells. Retention was significantly higher ($p < 0.01$) in the 700°C column at $56 \pm 11\%$, while the 500°C biochar column outperformed the others ($p < 0.01$), capturing $87 \pm 9\%$ of filtered bacteria. Backwashing of all three columns after filtration (phase v) resulted in an initial bacterial release equal to or exceeding the initially filtered amounts (capped at 1 in Figure 4A). In terms of mass balance, while the 300°C and 700°C columns effectively accumulated minimal bacteria after backwashing, the total capacity for accumulation of the 500°C column was 55.2% of filtered cells, highlighting its potential for application in quaternary treatment of wastewater.

For 1- μm MPs (Figure 4B), the columns exhibited significantly different behaviors ($p < 0.01$), though none approached saturation, as C_t remained consistently below C_0 . The 500°C column achieved the highest retention ($99.2 \pm 0.3\%$ of filtered 1- μm MPs), with nearly no MPs detected in the effluent of the filtration tests, followed by the 700°C column ($85 \pm 6\%$). The more oscillatory removal behavior observed in the 300°C biochar ($73 \pm 13\%$) is likely attributed to its less developed pore structure (Figure 3D), which remains more similar to the raw unheated material (Figure 3C). Backwashing led to a partial remobilization of previously retained MPs in the 500°C and 700°C columns, with release rates of $12 \pm 6\%$ and $32 \pm 12\%$, respectively, whereas the 300°C column released only $6.2 \pm 1.5\%$ of retained MPs. However, unlike bacteria, MPs are more deeply retained within biochar's porous structure and undergo limited resuspension during water and air backwashing, suggesting additional retardation mechanisms beyond surface interactions, as confirmed by SEM imaging (Figure 5).

Microscopic observation of the retained MPs and bacteria

At the end of the tests, biochar was extracted from the columns and samples underwent SEM imaging. 1- μm MPs were observed: (A) trapped deep within biochar's porous structure, (B) stuck in the gaps between the filter particles, (C) entangled by flaky biochar fragments, and (D) attached, presumably, to microorganisms also captured within the column, further contributing to their immobilisation (Figure 5).

Figure 5. SEM images of SCG-B with 1- μm MPs (A) trapped, (B) stuck, (C) entangled and (D) attached presumably to microorganisms.

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